

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF INDEPENDENT STUDY POLICY IMPLEMENTATION IN IMPROVING TEACHER'S COMPETENCE IN PUBLIC SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL HEAD OF BRANCH OFFICE REGION XI GARUT REGENCY WEST JAVA PROVINCE

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Abstract

This research is motivated by the issuance of the Circular Letter of the Minister of Education and Technology No. 1 of 2020 which was used as the initial momentum for the establishment of the Free Learning Policy through one of its programs, namely the teacher program as an effort to improve the quality of education in Indonesia. This research method uses a qualitative approach, with data collection interviews, observations and observations. The results showed that: first; The Motivating Teacher program with the support of professional staff in a hybrid way through LMS, individual mentoring and workshops, as well as training strategies with collaborative reflectiveness are quite successful in increasing teacher competence, both pedagogic, professional, personality and social competencies of State Senior High School teachers at the District XI Regional Office Branch Office arrowroot. Second; the obstacles faced are the long duration that makes them bored and tired, as well as the absence of a monitoring and evaluation program for empowering the driving teacher. Third: efforts are being made to overcome obstacles, namely by shortening the duration of time and integrating the training flow, as well as starting dissemination for driving teachers.

Keyword: effectiveness, driving teacher, competence

A. Introduction

The quality of education in Indonesia is still at a low level compared to other countries. This is based on the results of the 2018 PISA (Programme International Student Association) survey which concluded that the quality of Indonesian education was ranked 72 out of 77 countries surveyed. This is reinforced by the results of the 2016 GEM (Global Education Monitoring) which states that Indonesia's education is ranked 10th out of 14 developing countries and with an assessment of teacher quality is ranked 14th. The importance of the role of teachers in improving the quality of education is fully realized by all parties. In fact, on the official website of the Ministry of Education and Culture.go.id in 2020, it provides a detailed description of the UKG 2020 results, as follows: Overall the average value of the 2020 Teacher Competency Test in Indonesia is 53.2. This is still below the maximum standard target value expected by the government, which is 80. With these results it clearly shows that teacher competence is still not as expected.

The Free Learning Policy which was initiated by the government through Circular Letter of the Minister of Education and Technology No. 1 on 7 February 2020 is one of the government's efforts to improve the quality of Indonesian education in accordance with the demands of the times and people's expectations. This free learning policy is accompanied by various implementation programs that involve all aspects and components of Indonesian education. Until this research was carried out, there had been 15 episodes of the implementation of the independent learning policy program. The implementation of the independent learning policy which is specifically related to teacher competency improvement is the 5th episode of independent learning, namely the driving teacher. The West Java Provincial Education Office is an autonomous region that is part of the decentralized system of the Indonesian education system. In the organizational structure of the West Java education office, there is a division of work areas which are divided into XIII Branch Offices with defined areas. Garut Regency, West Java Province, is a Branch Office of the Regional XI Service. As part of Indonesia's national education system, the Regional XI Branch Office also implements the Independent Learning policy with its implementation programs. One of them is the driving teacher education program.

B. Methodology

This study uses a qualitative approach. According to qualitative research is "a method of investigating and understanding the meaning that a number of individuals or groups of people perceive as a social or humanitarian problem" (Shrestha & Bhattarai, 2022). Case studies according to Yin (2011) are qualitative research strategies that are relevant to situations where if the research question is how and why, it does not require control over the events being studied and focuses on contemporary events. Furthermore, according to (Nur'aini, 2020), the steps of case study research are: selecting themes, topics and cases, literature review, formulating research focus and problems, data collection, data improvement, data processing, data analysis process, conclusion of research results. and research reports (Septiana, 2021).

C. Result

1. The Effectiveness of the Implementation of the Independent Learning Policy in Improving the Competence of State High School Teachers Through the Teacher Motivator Program at the Regional XI Branch Office of Garut Regency, West Java Province

The study, entitled Effectiveness of the implementation of the independent learning policy in improving teacher competence at the Branch Office of the District XI Garut district, West Java province, is a comprehensive study on the implementation of the independent learning policy in the education system along with the achievement of the goals that have been achieved from implementation to implementation. when this research was conducted.

a. Successful Implementation Of The Program

The effectiveness of the program can be carried out with operational capabilities in carrying out work programs that are in accordance with predetermined objectives. The success of the program can be seen from the process and mechanism of an activity carried out in the field. Based on the results of interviews, observations and documentation studies, it shows that the mechanism for improving teacher competence through the teacher driving program is carried out in the following stages:

- Determination of the number of quotas and target areas by the Ministry of Education and Culture. The number of quotas for personnel is determined and the target areas are distributed evenly throughout the districts throughout the territory of Indonesia in rotation and continuously. Determination of the target area is carried out with the following criteria: representing 6 regions in Indonesia (Sumatra, Java, Kalimantan, Bali and Nusa Tenggara, Sulawesi, and Papua and Maluku); the needs of school principals in each district; areas that have internet access; non-disadvantaged areas. These criteria are an effort to ensure the effectiveness of the education program that will be carried out.
- Selection of Prospective Teachers. This selection is carried out to recruit superior teachers who have the potential to support the goal of independent learning. Selection stages: CV and essay tests, scholastic talent, teaching simulation tests and interviews. Until this research is carried out, the government is currently conducting the 7th batch selection according to a predetermined schedule.
- Driving Teacher Education. Implemented 9 months in a hybrid way (online and face-to-face) supported by a team of trained professional experts, modules compiled by experts in their fields. The government has implemented and is currently carrying out teacher training up to the 4th batch. Everything is going according to the planned procedure.
- Graduated as driving teacher with 360 hour certificate.

The process of increasing teacher competence through the teacher mobilization program is carried out with 9 months of planned and conceptualized teacher education. The success of the educational process in the teacher mobilization program can be seen in the following points:

- Education for 9 months is carried out in a hybrid manner, namely a combination of online, virtual and face-to-face education. This educational technique provides energy and time efficiency. Teachers can still follow the driving teacher education in their respective places without having to leave their teaching obligations.
- The flow of “MERDEKA” education in each module, starting from building CGP intrinsic motivation, understanding new material concepts, collaborative and reflective action based on understanding the module, and real action by doing direct practice in their respective schools. All of the training materials and techniques were new for the driving teachers and there was a change in mindset and an increase in the competence of the driving teachers.

- Human resources supporting education are experts and professionals who have gone through a selection process as well as training, namely resource persons, instructors, facilitators, and practical teachers. All supporters are able to carry out their duties with full responsibility in supporting the effectiveness of achieving the goals of the driving teacher program.
- Supporting infrastructure for teacher education, namely LMS and modules. Prior to starting education, prospective driving teachers are given training in using the LMS application and module technical guidance from resource persons and instructors. So that when education takes place, teachers are able to carry it out well.
- Assessment of driving teachers based on the tasks of achieving module material competencies through LMS, concrete actions in individual mentoring activities and workshops. In addition to understanding the material, in teacher education, movers are required to practice directly and show the results of the work of the material concepts they already understand. Assessment methods that are vertical and horizontal are able to provide feedback evaluations in assessing each other's success during the educational process.

Mechanisms and processes in the driving teacher education program as a whole have been going well according to the plan.

b. Goal Success

The effectiveness of target success is viewed from the point of view of achieving goals by focusing on the output aspect, meaning that effectiveness can be measured by how far the level of output in the policies and procedures of the organization to achieve the goals that have been set. The target in the teacher mover program is the teacher. The target of teachers expected by the Ministry of Education and Culture is teachers who have the competence to support the achievement of the objectives of the program and policy of independent learning. The efforts that have been made by the government in the teacher driving program show the following levels of target success:

1. The number of quotas and target areas for batches 1 and 2 that have been determined by the Ministry of Education and Culture has been reached. The number of registrants for driving teachers is 8 to 10 times the expected quota in each region.
2. With the large number of registrants, competition in the selection is tighter so that the government can actually recruit competent teachers to support the implementation of the driving teacher program. Teachers who have passed the selection are then determined to be mover teacher candidates and are required to take driving teacher education.
3. The 9 months of driving teacher education can be followed optimally by all prospective driving teachers. In particular, for prospective teachers of class 1 and 2 at the State Senior High School at the Branch Office of the District XI Garut district, all of them have attended education and have successfully graduated in education and received good and excellent achievements.

The description above shows that the success of the targets in the teacher mobilization program has achieved the expected goals, both the number of quotas and the target area, the competence of supporting teachers expected in the selection, as well as the completion of the education that has been determined.

c. Satisfaction with Program

An effectiveness criterion that refers to the success of the program in meeting user needs. Satisfaction is felt by users with the quality of the product or service produced. The higher the quality of the products and services provided, the higher the satisfaction felt by users, which can lead to benefits for the institution. Satisfaction with the driving teacher education program, the researchers got from the driving teachers who have attended education and managed to graduate with a satisfactory predicate. The description of their satisfaction with the driving teacher education program is as follows:

1. The support team actually carries out their duties and responsibilities in a professional manner. The effective and intimate communication system that exists in teacher education provides comfort for participants in teacher education. The facilitators really assess the achievement of their competencies through the module assignments uploaded to the LMS. The point of success can be directly evaluated. Practicing teachers position themselves as discussion partners and provide the flexibility to give appreciation for their learning achievements.
2. The materials delivered through the module are new materials that really open their horizons and knowledge in carrying out their profession as teachers as well as educational practitioners. The driving teachers stated that during their education they felt open-minded to become a better teacher in their dedication to student progress.
3. The combination training method provides convenience and efficiency in time. Participant of driving teacher education attends 9 months of education in their respective places without leaving their professional obligations and other individual obligations. The combination of virtual, online and face-to-face learning is a new thing in training.
4. The independent training flow is able to provide comprehensive competency development in driving teachers both internally and internally. Starting from self-motivation, emotional and social learning, as well as understanding new concepts, reflective actions in learning, and collaborative activities with other individuals in educational leadership. This has succeeded in increasing their competence to support their profession and growing confidence in carrying out activities that support the independent learning policy.

The outline of the results of the study shows the satisfaction of the driving teachers during the education of the driving teachers. And morally they are able to implement in carrying out their profession in the world of education. they feel proud to be a driving teacher and show progress in their competence in learning.

d. Input and Output Level

The success of increasing the competence of driving teachers can be seen by comparing the changes in the competences of the previous and after implementing the teacher's education. Changes in these competencies can be seen in the table below:

**Table 1: Comparison of Teacher Competency Inputs and Outputs
In the Motivating Teacher Education Program**

Competence	Competency Input	Educational Process	Output (Competency Improvement)
Pedagogic	The teacher plans, implements and evaluates learning with the concepts and standard methods determined by the teacher	Differentiated learning	Teachers plan, implement and evaluate learning with varied methods and involve students by adjusting the potential of each student. (differentiated RPP)
	The teacher is not careful with each student's character	Coaching	The teacher communicates openly with students to understand the potential and character of each student
	Conventional method of lecture	Differentiated learning	Creative and innovative learning methods favored by students
	The teacher gives a way out of solving problems for students	Differentiated learning	The teacher directs students to find their own solutions to the problems they face. (critical thinking)
	The teacher carries out his duties and obligations according to the demands of the applicable rules	Kihajar Dewantara's educational philosophy concept	Teachers have the motivation to do full dedication in the development and success of students.
	Teachers are less able to motivate students as a whole to like learning	Differentiated learning and coaching	Teachers carry out varied learning so that students are actively learning and enjoy learning.
Professional	The teacher is fixated on the material and scientific structure he gets in his studies.	Differentiated learning	Teachers make efforts to improve the material and scientific structure of their field of study in order to support student-centered learning
	Teachers are comfortable with the lecture method and are not motivated to innovate learning according to the demands of society and the times	Differentiated learning	Teachers are able to innovate to integrate learning in their field of study with technological developments.
Personality	The teacher's service is limited to his profession and duties	Kihajar Dewantara's educational philosophy concept	Teachers are aware of the dedication of the teaching profession in teaching success to develop the potential of each individual student, the hope of the nation
	The teacher realizes that he is a role model for students but is unable to manage his attitude and emotions	Emotional and social learning	The teacher shows emotional control in being patient and painstaking in dealing with various student characters
	The teacher motivates the whole class	Emotional and social learning	The teacher gives personal motivation to students in the class

Competence	Competency Input	Educational Process	Output (Competency Improvement)
	Lack of courage to innovate in teaching for fear of failure	Emotional and social learning	Confident in innovating teaching and evaluating its success.
Social	Teachers communicate effectively with colleagues who are considered understanding	Emotional and social learning	The teacher shows an increase in the ability to communicate with various individual characters.
	Lack of confidence when appearing in public forums		Increased confidence in speaking in community discussion forums and other public forums.
	Not confident in inviting others to innovate learning	Emotional and social learning	Have the motivation and confidence to move peers and other individuals in learning innovation
	Teachers tend to be authoritarian towards students in learning agreements		The teacher communicates intimately and effectively with students in learning

Source: Research Results, 2022.

Overall, changes in mindset and competency development in education can be implemented by the driving teacher in carrying out his profession according to the role of the driving teacher in supporting the achievement of the goal of independent learning. The achievement of driving teacher competence is also seen from the following points:

- Students enjoy learning and follow the whole learning process without burden or coercion. This can be seen from the enthusiasm of students when participating in learning from start to finish.
- Students show increased critical reasoning power. When interviewed by the researcher, students gave directed responses to the problems that occurred in learning and were able to find their own solutions.
- Improved student academic achievement. When students are given assignments with freedom of exploration based on their favorite technique or material, they manage to complete the task well and even exceed the teacher's expectations.
- Increasing the competence of driving teachers is able to motivate other teachers to be interested in participating in the driving teacher program. The driving teacher also looks sociable in communication and familiar with the students.
- The principal appreciates both the driving teacher in carrying out his profession. In addition to giving pride to the school, driving teachers are able to show various innovations in learning and make suggestions for school development.

e. Overall Goal Achievement

The driving teacher education program as part of the independent learning policy has a general goal, namely to produce teachers as agents of educational transformation towards achieving the goal of independent learning, namely learning that is pro-student, able to mobilize peers and the community in developing the school ecosystem into the values of the post-casila

student profile. Meanwhile, the specific objectives of the driving teacher program in improving teacher competence consist of 5 objectives. The results of the research on the achievement of the specific objectives of the driving teacher program are described below:

1. Develop yourself and other teachers by self-reflection, sharing and collaboration; The driving teacher education with the collaborative reflective training method has succeeded in developing the competence of each individual teacher. This can be seen during individual mentoring, which almost all of CGP's have implemented differentiation learning. The success of self-development of the driving teacher can also be seen in the products and programs exhibited during the workshop. The self-development of the driving teacher is also seen when learning takes place, students are very motivated and enthusiastic about participating in learning.
2. Have moral, emotional and spiritual maturity to behave according to the code of ethics; The moral, emotional and spiritual maturity of the driving teacher can be seen from his attitude in controlling and controlling attitudes during learning or when communicating with other individuals. During learning, the driving teacher is able to bring a learning atmosphere that increases student motivation to take part in learning. Motivating teachers are also able to be calm and focused in dealing with various student problems in learning. Students also look comfortable and familiar with the teacher both in learning and outside learning.
3. Planning, implementing, reflecting and evaluating student-centered learning by involving parents; In observations during the research, all Motivating Teachers have implemented differentiation learning and coaching. Differentiated RPP has been implemented according to the differentiation method. In learning, they have carried out according to differentiated RPP by instilling the values of the Pancasila student profile. For example, by implementing group learning according to the interests and potential of each student, quizzes and project-based learning. The teacher no longer intervenes in the material and assignments but only provides an outline of competency achievement and directs students to carry out tasks according to the techniques they like.
4. Collaborate with parents and communities to develop schools and foster student leadership; Motivating teachers are required to be able to collaborate with parents and the community in developing schools. In driving teacher education, they have received material on building school culture and have been able to plan school development programs in workshops and individual mentoring. However, in its implementation, the driving teachers have not been able to carry it out optimally due to various problems.
5. Develop and lead efforts to realize the school's vision that favors students and is relevant to the needs of the community around the school; Competently, the driving teachers already have scientific rules about this matter so they are required to be able to implement it in their respective schools.

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that the effectiveness of the implementation of the driving teacher in achieving the overall goals of the teacher driving program as part of the independent learning policy is illustrated in the table below

Table 2 :Pencapaian Tujuan Menyeluruh Program Guru Penggerak

No	Eexpected	Achievement
1	Develop yourself and other teachers by self-reflection, sharing and collaboration	Self-development is optimal, but developing other teachers independently and in collaboration has not been effective.
2	Have moral, emotional and spiritual maturity to behave according to the code of ethics	Overall, the driving teacher already has moral, emotional and spiritual maturity in a code of ethics.
3	Plan, implement, reflect and evaluate student-centred learning with parent involvement	All driving teachers have planned, implemented and evaluated student-centered learning, but have not optimally involved the role of parents.
4	Collaborate with parents and the community to develop the school and foster student leadership	Dalam menumbuhkan kepemimpinan individu murid In developing individual student leadership, it has been successfully implemented, but in collaborating with parents and the community it is still being carried out due to various problems.
5	Develop and lead efforts to realize a school vision that is pro-student and relevant to the needs of the community around the school	Developing the school's vision as a whole is not carried out by the driving teacher because the school's vision is already in favor of students and is relevant to the needs of the community. In an effort to develop and lead efforts to realize the school's vision, it has not been implemented because of the constraints of the school's bureaucratic structure.

Source: Research Results, 2022.

The table above shows that the achievement of the overall objectives of the driving teacher program in the implementation of the independent learning policy has not been optimal. The improvement of teacher competence through driving teachers has succeeded in showing significant changes and each driving teacher has been able to implement it in the learning of the field of study he is teaching. However, in mobilizing the community and developing schools, it has not been implemented optimally due to various problems.

2. Obstacles to the Implementation of the Independent Learning Policy in Improving the Competence of State High School Teachers at the Regional XI Branch Office, Garut Regency, West Java Province

Based on the results of research regarding the constraints on increasing the competence of State Senior High School teachers through the teacher mover program at the XI Regional Office Branch Office, Garut Regency, West Java Province, the outline is as follows:

- a. Bills for module assignments, individual mentoring and workshops, which are tightly scheduled and on an ongoing basis, are quite a drain on energy and time for CGPs. This is the reason for the delay in depositing the assigned module assignments through the LMS.

- b. Lack of support from superiors both during education and during the implementation of innovation programs in the school environment. CGPs have a little difficulty communicating various programs to school principals for various reasons, for example, the activity or the proposed program requires infrastructure that must be planned in the RAKS. The absence of the principal in individual mentoring causes schedule delays and confusion in the assessment by practical teachers.
- c. The implementation of differentiated learning and coaching is less effective in online learning during the covid-19 pandemic. This is due to the limitations of communication which can only be done through chat or face-to-face virtual with a relatively short time. So that teachers find it difficult to understand the various characters and potentials of each student.
- d. Differentiated learning and coaching methods do not reach all students effectively, especially students who are already familiar with the lecture learning method. The varied learning methods caused some students to be less focused in understanding the material and tend to be less serious in learning.
- e. There are no evaluation and monitoring activities on the continuation of innovation programs by teachers who are driving teachers in learning and in their respective communities. School supervisors and regional KCDs have no official duties for these money activities. In the absence of monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of programs by the driving teacher, it is feared that the driving teacher will lose moral responsibility and return to the old learning.

3. Efforts to Overcome Obstacles to the Implementation of the Free Learning Policy in Improving the Competence of State High School Teachers at the Regional XI Branch Office, Garut Regency, West Java Province

Efforts made in overcoming obstacles to the implementation of the independent policy through the teacher education program are comprehensive in nature based on direct policies from the Ministry of Education and Culture through the ranks of the implementers of the driving teacher program, namely:

- a. Streamlining and integrating module materials and activities in teacher education drive. Merdeka training stages (8 stages) were streamlined to Merdeka (7 stages). Individual mentoring activities that were originally 9 times became 7 times. And the workshop activity which was originally 9 times became 7 times. By streamlining and integrating this is an effort to reduce boredom, the burden of time and energy on teachers who take part in teacher education. So that it is more effective in increasing competence.
- b. The addition of the teacher mobilization quota began with the education of driving teachers for the 6th generation. Initially as many as 2800 teachers for all of Indonesia, it became 8000 teachers. With the addition of the quota, it is hoped that the number of teacher educators in each school community will increase so that there will be more personnel in implementing teacher teacher programs.

- c. The increase in the principal's support for the driving teacher program is carried out by the school supervisor. School supervisors remind principals of their obligations as government officials to support all programs in education policies imposed by the government.
- d. In an effort to implement student-friendly learning, teachers apply differentiated learning to develop the character and potential of each student. To understand the various characters and potentials of each individual student, the driving teacher communicates and discusses both with the homeroom teacher, other teachers and or with the students themselves.
- e. The Ministry of Education and Culture has directly appointed P4TK TK and PLB West Java to carry out follow-up programs for early morning teachers, including at the Branch Office of the XI Regional Office of Garut Regency. P4TK has conducted special training for teacher mobilizers in Garut Regency batch 1 so that driving teachers remain consistent in implementing programs according to the educational objectives of driving teachers. This training aims to refresh the material that has been provided during teacher training, and evaluate the implementation and dissemination of teacher educators in their respective communities. The program will continue to be implemented continuously for all teacher movers.

The efforts described above have been carried out holistically by P4TK TK and PLB West Java and self-paced teachers with support from various related parties.

D. Discussion

The achievement of the objectives of the teacher education program, especially for high school teachers at the Regional XI Branch Office, Garut Regency, West Java Province, has been effective in increasing teacher competence in terms of pedagogic, professional, personality and social competencies. The driving teacher has been able to carry out student-friendly learning by instilling the values of the Pancasila student profile. However, the implementation of innovation programs to mobilize and develop schools has not been achieved optimally according to the expected goals. Until the time of this study, there were no direct monitoring and evaluation activities for the driving teacher. This is a concern for the competence of teachers that have been obtained in teacher education, the movement is not carried out, but returns to the habit of the previous way of learning.

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